

Supplementary Information for:

Estimation of species divergence times in presence of cross-species gene flow

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Supplementary Methods

Parameter estimates from simulated data

Parameters were estimated from simulated data with BPP v4.1.4 for both the MSC and MSci models. Both analyses used a single MCMC chain that collected 200,000 posterior samples after a burnin of 20,000 and saving every 2 samples. The prior on θ was an inverse gamma with a shape (α) of 3 and scale (β) of $\theta \times 2$. This centers the prior distribution on the true value of θ since the inverse gamma distribution has a mean of $\frac{\beta}{(\alpha-1)}$. Similarly, the prior distribution on the root τ was an inverse gamma with $\alpha = 3$ and $\beta = \theta \times 6$. All other τ then follow a uniform Dirichlet distribution with $\alpha = 3$. For the MSci model only, a prior Beta distribution with both shape parameters set at 1 was specified on φ , which is equivalent to the uniform distribution for the interval from 0 to 1. Visual inspection of a few analyses from the simulated data were done to assure MCMC settings were appropriate, and that parameter estimates had converged.

Additional scrutiny was given to seemingly abhorrent values such as θ estimates using the MSC for the non-sister and ghost lineage simulations under IM. Inspection of posteriors revealed that some replicates converged to the true value with efficient MCMC sampling while some tended to sample extreme values that generated biologically unrealistic means and wide HPD intervals despite the posterior median being very close to the true value. Were we to collect many more MCMC samples for these simulation analyses with poorly estimated θ from the MSC model, it is reasonable to expect improved estimates. However, we present these estimates as poor MCMC sampling is a reality of empirical data analysis, and this further demonstrates some advantages of MSci despite modeling gene flow as an episodic event as opposed to the IM generating model that assumes gene flow is continuous.

Calibrating divergence times

We considered two common approaches for calibrating divergence times measured in substitutions per site to years. First, we use a node calibration on the root, which could come from fossil evidence placed near the crown of a group (e.g. Benton and Donoghue 2007) or a well-justified geological event (e.g. Da Baets et al. 2016). Second, we used a mutation rate calibration. When measured with some degree of reason a de novo mutation rate could be used to calibrate divergence times (Yoder and Tiley 2021), or a phylogenetic substitution rate from a previous study (Campbell et al. 2021). The choice of calibration is up to an investigator to determine the best strategy for their group, but we make the comparison here since a rate calibration will depend on the absolute node differences between models (as presented in our simulation results), while a node calibration depends only on the relative distances between nodes. The differences between calibration strategies could lead to different conclusions about absolute ages between the MSC and MSci models. For example a root node with an age of 0.01 in substitutions per site under the MSC and 0.02 substitutions per site un the MSci would both have an age of 10 Ma ago if the same node calibration were applied. However, a rate calibration applied to all nodes of a tree would cause the MSci root divergence time to be twice as old as the MSC divergence time.

Here we apply only the simplest of node calibrations and rate calibrations estimated in a somewhat crude manner, but they serve as tools for demonstrating differences between the MSci and MSC model with real data rather than authoritative investigations of the best possible calibrations for the two genera examined here. Since the rate calibration presented was based on substitutions per-site from the MSC analyses and we adhere to a strict molecular clock, the node-calibrated and rate-calibrated MSC analyses are equivalent.

Baobabs

We assumed that the sampled outgroup *Scleronema* diverged from *Adansonia* 18.2 Ma ago (Marinho et al. 2014). Node-calibrated divergence times for both MSC and MSci analyses were generated by setting the mean posterior estimate of τ_c (Supplementary Figure S25) to 18.2 and rescaling all other mean estimates and HPD intervals by $\frac{\text{node height}}{\tau_c} \times 18.2$. A rate calibration in substitutions per site per million years was obtained from the MSC by $rate = \frac{\tau_c}{18.2} = \frac{0.012883}{18.2} = 0.00070786$. The rate-calibrated MSci estimates were then generated by $\frac{\text{node height}}{rate}$. Although this ignores selection acting on sites analyzed here, it works for our demonstrative purposes. All MSC and MSci estimates in substitutions per site are available in Supplementary Table S1 and calculating the calibrated values is trivial given the assumption of a strict clock.

Jaltomata

The process for deriving node-calibrated and rate-calibrated divergence times was the same as for baobabs, but assuming that *Solanum* and *Jaltomata* diverged 17 Ma ago (Sarkinen et al. 2013). This root node is τ_a (Supplementary Figure S32). All node heights for the MSC and MSci models in substitutions per site are in Supplementary Table S2.

Supplementary Figures

Figure S1 – Divergence Time Estimates for Sister Lineages under the MSC. Points are posterior means and error bars are 95% highest posterior densities. Dashed lines are true values. Node labels and divergence times correspond to Fig. 1a.

Figure S2 – Divergence Time and Introgression Probability Estimates for Sister Lineages under the MSci. Points are posterior means and error bars are 95% highest posterior densities. Dashed lines are true values. Node labels and divergence times correspond to Fig. 1a.

Figure S3 – Divergence Time Estimates for Non-Sister Lineages under the MSC. Points are posterior means and error bars are 95% highest posterior densities. Dashed lines are true values. Node labels and divergence times correspond to Fig. 1b.

Figure S4 – Divergence Time and Introgression Probability Estimates for Non-Sister Lineages under the MSci. Points are posterior means and error bars are 95% highest posterior densities. Dashed lines are true values. Node labels and divergence times correspond to Fig. 1b.

Figure S5 – Divergence Time Estimates for Ghost Lineage under the MSC. Points are posterior means and error bars are 95% highest posterior densities. Dashed lines are true values. Node labels and divergence times correspond to Fig. 1c.

Figure S6 – Divergence Time and Introgression Probability Estimates for Ghost Lineage under the MSci. Points are posterior means and error bars are 95% highest posterior densities. Dashed lines are true values. Node labels and divergence times correspond to Fig. 1c.

Figure S7 – Population Size Estimates for Sister Lineages under the MSC. Points are posterior means and error bars are 95% highest posterior densities. Dashed lines are true values. Node labels and populations sizes correspond to Fig. 1a.

Figure S8 – Population Size Estimates for Sister Lineages under the MSci. Points are posterior means and error bars are 95% highest posterior densities. Dashed lines are true values. Node labels and population sizes correspond to Fig. 1a.

Figure S9 – Population Size Estimates for Non-Sister Lineages under the MSC. Points are posterior means and error bars are 95% highest posterior densities. Dashed lines are true values. Node labels and population sizes correspond to Fig. 1b.

Figure S10 – Population Size Estimates for Non-Sister Lineages under the MSci. Points are posterior means and error bars are 95% highest posterior densities. Dashed lines are true values. Node labels and population sizes correspond to Fig. 1b.

Figure S11 – Population Size Estimates for Ghost Lineage under the MSC. Points are posterior means and error bars are 95% highest posterior densities. Dashed lines are true values. Node labels and population sizes correspond to Fig. 1c.

Figure S12 – Population Size Estimates for Ghost Lineage under the MSci. Points are posterior means and error bars are 95% highest posterior densities. Dashed lines are true values. Node labels and population sizes correspond to Fig. 1c.

Figure S13 – Divergence Time Estimates from IM Simulations for Sister Lineages under the MSC. Points are posterior means and error bars are 95% highest posterior densities. Dashed lines are true values. Node labels and divergence times correspond to Fig. 1a. Nm is the mutation-scaled immigration rate.

Figure S14 – Divergence Time and Introgression Probability Estimates from IM Simulations for Sister Lineages under the MSci. Points are posterior means and error bars are 95% highest posterior densities. Dashed lines are true values. Node labels and divergence times correspond to Fig. 1a. Nm is the mutation-scaled immigration rate, so there is no known value for ϕ_h .

Figure S15 – Divergence Time Estimates from IM Simulations for Non-Sister Lineages under the MSC. Points are posterior means and error bars are 95% highest posterior densities. Dashed lines are true values. Node labels and divergence times correspond to Fig. 1b. Nm is the mutation-scaled immigration rate.

Figure S16 – Divergence Time and Introgression Probability Estimates from IM Simulations for Non-Sister Lineages under the MSci. Points are posterior means and error bars are 95% highest posterior densities. Dashed lines are true values. Node labels and divergence times correspond to Fig. 1b. Nm is the mutation-scaled immigration rate, so there is no known value for φ_h .

Figure S17 – Divergence Time Estimates from IM Simulations for Ghost Lineage under the MSC. Points are posterior means and error bars are 95% highest posterior densities. Dashed lines are true values. Node labels and divergence times correspond to Fig. 1c. Nm is the mutation-scaled immigration rate.

Figure S18 – Divergence Time and Introgression Probability Estimates from IM Simulations for Ghost Lineage under the MSci. Points are posterior means and error bars are 95% highest posterior densities. Dashed lines are true values. Node labels and divergence times correspond to Fig. 1c. Nm is the mutation-scaled immigration rate, so there is no known value for φ_h .

Figure S19 – Population Size Estimates from IM Simulations for Sister Lineages under the MSC. Points are posterior means and error bars are 95% highest posterior densities. Dashed lines are true values. Node labels and populations sizes correspond to Fig. 1a. Nm is the mutation-scaled immigration rate.

Figure S20 – Population Size Estimates from IM Simulations for Sister Lineages under the MSci. Points are posterior means and error bars are 95% highest posterior densities. Dashed lines are true values. Node labels and population sizes correspond to Fig. 1a. Nm is the mutation-scaled immigration rate.

Figure S21 – Population Size Estimates from IM Simulations for Non-Sister Lineages under the MSC. Points are posterior means and error bars are 95% highest posterior densities. Dashed lines are true values. Node labels and population sizes correspond to Fig. 1b. Nm is the mutation-scaled immigration rate.

Figure S22 – Population Size Estimates from IM Simulations for Non-Sister Lineages under the MSci. Points are posterior means and error bars are 95% highest posterior densities. Dashed lines are true values. Node labels and population sizes correspond to Fig. 1b. Nm is the mutation-scaled immigration rate.

Figure S23 – Population Size Estimates from IM Simulations for Ghost Lineage under the MSC. Points are posterior means and error bars are 95% highest posterior densities. Dashed lines are true values. Node labels and population sizes correspond to Fig. 1c. Nm is the mutation-scaled immigration rate.

Figure S24 – Population Size Estimates from IM Simulations for Ghost Lineage under the MSci. Points are posterior means and error bars are 95% highest posterior densities. Dashed lines are true values. Node labels and population sizes correspond to Fig. 1c. Nm is the mutation-scaled immigration rate.

Figure S25 – BPP Topology and Node Labels for *Adansonia*. Divergence time estimation used the inferred introgression events from PhyloNetworks. Letters are node labels that correspond to parameter estimates. Blue edges and letters represent introgression events and are only present in the MSci model.

Figure S26 – Population Size Estimates for *Adansonia* under the MSC. The four violin plots represent the four individual chains used for analysis.

Figure S27 – Divergence Time Estimates for *Adansonia* under the MSC. The four violin plots represent the four individual chains used for analysis. A scatterplot of median node heights for τ implies convergence of the MCMC analyses.

Figure S28 – Population Size Estimates for *Adansonia* under the MSci. The four violin plots represent the four individual chains used for analysis. Additional nodes for introgression events are represented here.

Figure S29 – Divergence Time Estimates for *Adansonia* under the MSci. The four violin plots represent the four individual chains used for analysis. The ϕ estimate for the Longitubae introgression event is also shown here, with the other edge represented by $1 - \phi$. The scatterplot of median node heights suggests convergence of divergence times.

Figure S30 – ASTRAL tree for *Jaltomata*. Numbers at nodes are local posterior probabilities. Coloring of tip labels and outlined clades indicate fruit color and follow the convention of the original study. The ASTRAL tree matches the original authors' concatenated ML tree with the exception of the switched placement of *J. dendroidea* and *J. incahuasina*. Unsurprisingly, this relationship has a low local posterior probability. Internal branch lengths are coalescent units $\left(\frac{2\tau}{\theta}\right)$, but terminal branch lengths are not estimated by ASTRAL and arbitrarily set to 1. Note that ASTRAL estimates unrooted trees and the species tree is rooted with *S. lycopersicum*, so the branch subtending the *Jaltomata* MRCA is arbitrarily 0.5.

Figure S31 – Best Network from PhyloNetworks for *Jaltomata*. The major topology is identical to the ASTRAL tree. Node labels indicate introgression events. The light blue color represents the minor topology and small inheritance probability. The dark blue color indicated the major topology and greater inheritance probability. These detected introgression events were used to estimate divergence times with BPP.

Figure S32 – BPP Topology and Node Labels. Divergence time estimation used the inferred introgression events from PhyloNetworks. Letters are node labels that correspond to parameter estimates. Blue edges and letters represent introgression events and are only present in the MSci model. A ghost lineage was included to model introgression from an unsampled lineage sister to *Jaltomata* into the MRCA of the green- and orange-fruited clades.

Figure S33 – Population Size Estimates for *Jaltomata* under the MSC. The four violin plots represent the four individual chains used for analysis.

Figure S34 – Divergence Time Estimates for *Jaltomata* under the MSC. The four violin plots represent the four individual chains used for analysis. A scatterplot of median node heights for τ implies convergence of divergence times from MCMC analyses. The root node is excluded from the scatterplot to improve visibility.

Figure S35 – Population Size Estimates for *Jaltomata* under the MSci. The four violin plots represent the four individual chains used for analysis. Additional nodes for introgression events are represented here.

Figure S36 – Divergence Time Estimates for *Jaltomata* under the MScI. The four violin plots represent the four individual chains used for analysis. Additional nodes for introgression events are represented here. The scatterplot of median node heights suggests convergence. The root node is excluded from the scatterplot to improve visibility.

Figure S37 – Introgression Probability Estimates for *Jaltomata* under the MSci. The four violin plots represent the four individual chains used for analysis. Both nodes involved in an introgression event are not plotted here because the other edge is simply $1 - \phi$.

Supplementary Tables

Introgression	Phi (<i>Nm</i>)	Theta	n-sites	n-seqs	MSci Simulations			IM Simulations		
					MSci	MSC	MSci:MSC	MSci	MSC	MSci:MSC
sister	0.05 (0.1)	0.001	100	2	4.79	3.24	1.48	8.53	6.18	1.38
sister	0.05 (0.1)	0.001	100	10	48.5	32.9	1.47	59.4	41	1.45
sister	0.05 (0.1)	0.001	500	2	6.52	5.01	1.30	10.1	7.18	1.41
sister	0.05 (0.1)	0.001	500	10	47.3	32.1	1.47	65.5	50.5	1.30
sister	0.05 (0.1)	0.01	100	2	9.73	6.46	1.51	10.9	8.91	1.22
sister	0.05 (0.1)	0.01	100	10	62.6	48.8	1.28	76.5	63.4	1.21
sister	0.05 (0.1)	0.01	500	2	9.95	7.22	1.38	13.8	10.6	1.30
sister	0.05 (0.1)	0.01	500	10	106	86.1	1.23	118	104	1.13
sister	0.2 (1)	0.001	100	2	7.45	5.04	1.48	9.78	6.72	1.46
sister	0.2 (1)	0.001	100	10	45.2	32.4	1.40	62.1	47	1.32
sister	0.2 (1)	0.001	500	2	7.38	4.58	1.61	10.7	7.45	1.44
sister	0.2 (1)	0.001	500	10	52.6	39.7	1.32	72.4	57.6	1.26
sister	0.2 (1)	0.01	100	2	7.63	4.78	1.60	11.7	8.66	1.35
sister	0.2 (1)	0.01	100	10	77.6	57.3	1.35	86.7	59.1	1.47
sister	0.2 (1)	0.01	500	2	13.2	9.38	1.41	13.7	9.95	1.38
sister	0.2 (1)	0.01	500	10	96.8	77.1	1.26	93.1	76.1	1.22
non-sister	0.05 (0.1)	0.001	100	2	6.87	4.58	1.50	5.95	3.72	1.60
non-sister	0.05 (0.1)	0.001	100	10	45.5	30.9	1.47	64	37.5	1.71
non-sister	0.05 (0.1)	0.001	500	2	8.47	5	1.69	7.62	5.12	1.49
non-sister	0.05 (0.1)	0.001	500	10	61.4	42	1.46	62.5	47.1	1.33
non-sister	0.05 (0.1)	0.01	100	2	9.69	5.08	1.91	8.74	5.03	1.74
non-sister	0.05 (0.1)	0.01	100	10	62.3	47.8	1.30	76.4	59.2	1.29
non-sister	0.05 (0.1)	0.01	500	2	11.4	7.9	1.44	9.71	6.98	1.39
non-sister	0.05 (0.1)	0.01	500	10	95.7	78.9	1.21	95.5	80	1.19
non-sister	0.2 (1)	0.001	100	2	7.8	5.65	1.38	7.58	5.32	1.42
non-sister	0.2 (1)	0.001	100	10	57.3	32.8	1.75	51.6	35.7	1.45
non-sister	0.2 (1)	0.001	500	2	13	7.45	1.74	9.78	6.6	1.48
non-sister	0.2 (1)	0.001	500	10	53.4	39.3	1.36	67.8	48.4	1.40
non-sister	0.2 (1)	0.01	100	2	8.01	5.48	1.46	21	11.1	1.89
non-sister	0.2 (1)	0.01	100	10	60.5	45.5	1.33	62.8	50.2	1.25
non-sister	0.2 (1)	0.01	500	2	9.99	7.06	1.42	21.7	18	1.21

non-sister	0.2 (1)	0.01	500	10	111	77	1.44	82.6	66.6	1.24
ghost	0.05 (0.1)	0.001	100	2	5.85	3.65	1.60	6.81	4.68	1.46
ghost	0.05 (0.1)	0.001	100	10	46	32.7	1.41	49.6	33.2	1.49
ghost	0.05 (0.1)	0.001	500	2	7.21	4.98	1.45	10.8	5.84	1.85
ghost	0.05 (0.1)	0.001	500	10	59.2	42	1.41	60.3	44.6	1.35
ghost	0.05 (0.1)	0.01	100	2	7.48	4.9	1.53	9.1	6.09	1.49
ghost	0.05 (0.1)	0.01	100	10	63.6	46.2	1.38	68.3	56	1.22
ghost	0.05 (0.1)	0.01	500	2	9.38	7.18	1.31	16.4	9.77	1.68
ghost	0.05 (0.1)	0.01	500	10	99.8	76.1	1.31	86.3	72.6	1.19
ghost	0.2 (1)	0.001	100	2	8.69	6.15	1.41	6.97	4.26	1.64
ghost	0.2 (1)	0.001	100	10	47.1	34.5	1.37	50.2	32.7	1.54
ghost	0.2 (1)	0.001	500	2	8.7	6.52	1.33	7.52	4.9	1.53
ghost	0.2 (1)	0.001	500	10	57.1	42.3	1.35	72.2	50.2	1.44
ghost	0.2 (1)	0.01	100	2	7.03	5.05	1.39	8.73	6.37	1.37
ghost	0.2 (1)	0.01	100	10	69.5	49.7	1.40	63.1	47.6	1.33
ghost	0.2 (1)	0.01	500	2	11.4	8.88	1.28	11.6	8.87	1.31
ghost	0.2 (1)	0.01	500	10	121	86	1.41	93.2	80.5	1.16
Average							1.43			1.40

Table S1 – Median runtime from simulations. The median time for the MCMC analysis among 10 replicates is given for each simulation condition under the MSci and MSC models. The ratio of runtimes between MSci and MSC analyses (MSci:MSC) shows the relative increases in computing time required for MSci analyses.

Node Label	MSC				MSci			
	Node Number	Mean	Lower 95% HPD	Upper 95% HPD	Node Number	Mean	Lower 95% HPD	Upper 95% HPD
c	9	0.012883	0.012278	0.013466	9	0.01283	0.012229	0.013434
d	10	0.006206	0.005994	0.006428	10	0.006192	0.005981	0.00641
e	11	0.005875	0.005644	0.006095	11	0.005881	0.005648	0.006101
w	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
x	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
h	14	0.002275	0.002091	0.002454	15	0.002245	0.002056	0.002424
f	12	0.004029	0.003889	0.004254	12	0.004343	0.004145	0.004552
y	NA	NA	NA	NA	13	0.002461	0.001942	0.002877
z	NA	NA	NA	NA	16	0.002461	0.001942	0.002877
i	15	0.001074	0.000999	0.001148	17	0.000978	0.000896	0.00106
j	16	0.00106	0.000987	0.001138	18	0.000965	0.00088	0.001044
g	13	0.003994	0.00386	0.004129	14	0.004203	0.00404	0.004365

Table S2 – Divergence Time Estimates for *Adansonia*. Node labels correspond to nodes in Figure S25. Node numbers correspond to parameter order in BPP log files available through Dryad.

Node Label	MSC				MSci			
	Node Number	Mean	Lower 95% HPD	Upper 95% HPD	Node Number	Mean	Lower 95% HPD	Upper 95% HPD
a	16	0.027963	0.027153	0.028723	16	0.028	0.027214	0.028789
t	NA	NA	NA	NA	17	0.004586	0.004341	0.004866
u	NA	NA	NA	NA	18	0.001977	0.001898	0.002057
b	17	0.004125	0.004032	0.00422	19	0.004259	0.004144	0.004369
c	18	0.003147	0.003063	0.003234	20	0.003315	0.003217	0.003412
w	NA	NA	NA	NA	21	0.002375	0.002156	0.002561
d	19	0.001995	0.001636	0.002332	22	0.002429	0.002233	0.00261
x	NA	NA	NA	NA	23	0.002375	0.002156	0.002561
e	20	0.002361	0.002297	0.002423	24	0.002386	0.002321	0.002449
v	NA	NA	NA	NA	25	0.001977	0.001898	0.002057
f	21	0.001817	0.001765	0.00187	26	0.001962	0.001885	0.002041
z	NA	NA	NA	NA	27	0.00095	0.000853	0.001032
g	22	0.000821	0.000721	0.000923	28	0.000517	0.000141	0.000828
h	23	0.001346	0.001276	0.001414	29	0.001374	0.001311	0.001442
i	24	0.00115	0.001079	0.001213	30	0.001165	0.001103	0.00122
j	25	0.000531	0.000438	0.000618	31	0.000521	0.000431	0.000608
k	26	0.000392	0.000119	0.000575	32	0.000387	0.00012	0.000566
l	27	0.001066	0.000981	0.00114	33	0.001103	0.001041	0.001164
m	28	0.000994	0.000879	0.001091	34	0.001057	0.000984	0.001123
n	29	0.000795	0.000563	0.000983	35	0.000976	0.000893	0.001053
y	NA	NA	NA	NA	36	0.00095	0.000853	0.001032

Table S3 – Divergence Time Estimates for *Jaltomata*. Node labels correspond to nodes in Figure S32. Node numbers correspond to parameter order in BPP log files available through Dryad.

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